

THEORETICAL PREDICTION OF EVOLUTION OF RANDOM FIBER BREAKAGES IN AN UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE UNDER SIMPLE TENSION

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ABSTRACT

The random fiber breakage evolution of unidirectional reinforced glass/epoxy composites under simple tension was described with poisson's process based on Rosen's experimental data of 1965. The relation between the probability of fiber breakage number and the current load was established. And the load corresponding to the occurrence of the first fiber breakage was also discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

The components of fiber composites consist of fibers, matrix and their interfaces. The stiffness and strength of fiber composites depend on the properties of these components and their damage evolution under the action of load or/and temperature¹. Various possible damage mode of a composite laminate, including fiber breakages, matrix cracks, interface debondings, delaminations and some of their combination depending on the laminate lay-ups will appear. In regard to the unidirectional reinforced fiber composite, its failure is the result of accumulation of dispersed fiber breakages, accompanying matrix cracks or/and interfacial debondings near the fiber breakages. Usually the damage process develops slowly and it will take time to lead the first fiber breakage to final rupture². So to study the mechanical properties of unidirectional fiber reinforced composites should begin with the criterion of occurrence of the first fiber breakage, then accumulation of random fiber breakage and end with the strength criterion. This paper focuses its attention to the random process of fiber breakage development. It aims to predict theoretically the probability distribution of fiber breakage number at an arbitrary load. At the end of this paper, the condition of the first fiber breakage was also briefly discussed.

2. ANALYSIS OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Rosen³ conducted an experimental research of fiber breakage for the unidirectional glass fiber reinforced epoxy composite under simple tension. Fig.1 shows the number of fiber breakages versus load. The codes A and B denote two kinds of glass epoxy composites with different resin formulae. Their respective moduli are $E_A=0.48 \times 10^6$ psi, and $E_B=0.277 \times 10^6$ psi. It can be seen that number of fiber breakage is a stochastic variable at certain load level. So the random fiber breakage evolution is a random process. Since the load is monotonously increased, the random process can be described in terms of load instead of time.

The accumulation of fiber breakage number is a counting process, so the Poisson's process was employed to describe the fiber breakage accumulation. The probability density of Poisson's process at time t is:

$$P[n(t)] = \frac{(\lambda t)^n}{n!} e^{-\lambda t} \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda(t)$ is Poisson's Coefficient, which denotes the increase rate of event at time t . Since the load increases monotonously with time, the difference between load f and

time t is only a multiplication factor. So in Eq.1 time t can be substituted with load f , and λ is now meant to be the average increasing rate of fiber breakages at certain load level. The curve in Fig.2, which indicates the relationship between the average number of fiber breakages and load, can be simplified with a bilinear line. In this case, λ in each segment is a constant. Table 1 shows the Poisson constant λ_1 of two successive segments for materials A and B. Difference of λ_1 and λ_2 between different materials depends not only on the mechanical properties of component materials, but also on the fabrication conditions. The intercept points of the first segment on the load abscissa and the intersecting points of successive segments are also presented in that table. The intercept points approximately indicate the average loads of onsets of the first fiber breakage. The intersecting point of two successive segments indicates that the damage mechanism switches to a new mode.

The loads corresponding to the intersecting points, i.e. 164.5 lb for material A and 152.7 lb for material B, can be proved with Zweben's multiple fracture formula⁴:

$$E_2 = MNP_2 \quad (2)$$

to be the loads at which multiple fiber-breakage begins to appear, where N is the total number of fibers, $M=L/\delta$, L the gage length of specimen, δ ineffective length and P_2 the probability that a given fiber will break followed by the fracture of at least one adjacent fiber. From this time on, λ_2 is about two times more than λ_1 , that is, the average rate of fiber breaking increases drastically. In the later stage, the multiple-fiber breakage causes significant stress concentration and the composite strength should be predicted with Zweben's model instead of damage-accumulation model which is too conservative in comparison with the experimental results³.

3. RANDOM DAMAGE EVOLUTION OF FIBER BREAKAGES IN UNIDIRECTIONAL GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE UNDER TENSION

As mentioned above the random evolution of fiber breakage can be described with Poisson's process:

$$P[n(f)] = \frac{[(f-f_0)]^n}{n!} e^{-\lambda(f-f_0)} \quad (3)$$

where n is the number of fiber breakages, λ indicates the damage evolution rate, f_0 is the load corresponding to the onset of fiber breakages and it can be determined either by experimental measurement or theoretical prediction.

Substituting the values of λ shown in Table 1 into Eq.3 and calculating f_0 by measuring the intercepts on load abscissa of the first straight segment of n - f curves in Fig.2, Eq.3 can be reduced to Eq.4 for material A and Eq.5 for material B:

$$P[n(f)] = \begin{cases} \frac{[0.072(f-44)]^n}{n!} e^{-0.072(f-44)} & 44 < f < 164.5 \\ \frac{[0.205(f-122)]^n}{n!} e^{-0.205(f-122)} & f > 164.5 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$P[n(f)] = \begin{cases} \frac{[0.09(f-84)]^n}{n!} e^{-0.09(f-84)} & 84 < f < 152.7 \\ \frac{[0.255(f-128)]^n}{n!} e^{-0.255(f-128)} & f > 152.7 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

With given loads, the damage probability density distribution curve can be drawn as shown in Fig.1a and 1b, where the given loads are 100lb, 120lb, 140lb, 160lb, 180lb, and 200lb respectively for material A and 100lb, 120lb, 140lb, 150lb, 170lb and 190lb respectively for material B. The results show that the theoretical probability den-

density distribution curves agree with experimental results quite well. The corresponding calculation results are presented in Table 2.

The relationship between the load and the damage probability in certain damage state can be obtained by Eq.4 and Eq.5. The strength of composites could be predicted if the failure probability and the average value of n of final rupture are known.

4. LOAD CORRESPONDING TO THE FIRST FIBER BREAKAGE

The load corresponding to the first fiber breakage was calculated by Zweben⁴ according to Rosen's model with:

$$E = MNF(\delta) \quad (6)$$

where N and M have same meanings as in Eq.2, and $F(\delta)$ is the distribution function of fiber breakage probability. The results indicate that predication based on Rosen's model is far too higher than the experimental results and the experimental load data corresponding to the first fiber breakage has a remarkable scatter. The authors believe that the corresponding to the first fiber breakage is dominated by inherent defect of composite materials and matrix crazing, so it can only be determined by means of experimental measurements.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

An unidirectional fiber reinforced composite material under simple tension will experience a long damage accumulation process before the final rupture. The site and number of fiber breakages are random, so the damage development should be described with an appropriate random process. In this paper the Poisson's process was proved to be such a random process which can be used to predict the damage state based on an initially known damage state.

The key factor is to determine the damage rate λ , and λ depends on the properties of component materials and fabrication process.

If the final damage state is known, the strength of composites can be predicted based on the relation between load and damage probability distribution.

As for the predication of load corresponding to the first fiber breakage, the inherent defects and matrix crazing play very important role. So it seems very difficult to do prediction theoretically.

REFERENCES

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Fig.1 (a)

Fig.1 (b)

Fig. 1 The relation between the fiber breakage load and fiber breakage distribution

Fig.2 (a)

Fig.2 (b)

Fig. 2 Simplified curve of fiber breakage number versus load

Table 1 Poisson constants, intercepts on the load abscissa and deflection points

λr	λ_1	λ_2	intercepts (p)	deflection points (p)
material A	0.072	0.205	44	164.5
material B	0.090	0.255	84	152.7

Table 2 Predicted probability density of fiber breakage number n

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
f(p)																								
100	0.072	0.144	0.914	0.195	0.158	0.102	0.061	0.031	0.014	0.006	0.002	0.001	0	0	0									
120	0.023	0.063	0.115	0.157	0.172	0.157	0.122	0.084	0.051	0.028	0.014	0.006	0.003	0.001	0									
140	0.007	0.024	0.055	0.097	0.131	0.151	0.149	0.129	0.099	0.068	0.043	0.025	0.013	0.006	0.003									
160	0.002	0.008	0.023	0.048	0.080	0.111	0.133	0.139	0.129	0.107	0.082	0.057	0.036	0.022	0.012									
180					0.014	0.027	0.046	0.068	0.090	0.107	0.115	0.114	0.105	0.089	0.070	0.052	0.037	0.024	0.015	0.009				
200					0.001	0.003	0.006	0.012	0.021	0.034	0.050	0.066	0.082	0.093	0.099	0.099	0.093	0.083	0.070	0.056	0.040	0.031	0.021	0.044

Material B

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
f(p)																								
100	0.340	0.246	0.118	0.042	0.012	0.003	0.001	0	0	0														
120	0.127	0.206	0.222	0.180	0.117	0.063	0.029	0.012	0.004	0.001														
140	0.033	0.082	0.138	0.174	0.175	0.147	0.106	0.067	0.031	0.019	0.009	0.004	0.001	0.001	0									
150	0.016	0.046	0.092	0.137	0.162	0.161	0.136	0.101	0.067	0.037	0.021	0.010	0.005	0.002	0.001									
170					0.026	0.047	0.072	0.096	0.114	0.122	0.119	0.106	0.087	0.067	0.048	0.032	0.020	0.012	0.008	0.005				
190										0.037	0.088	0.069	0.084	0.095	0.100	0.099	0.092	0.081	0.067	0.063	0.040	0.029	0.020	0.043